

A. Artifact Appendix

A.1 Abstract

This paper introduces the Automated Computing Library Tuner (Luthier), designed to optimize deep learning execution on asymmetric multi-core CPUs by selecting the most suitable kernels and distributing workloads efficiently. Utilizing existing kernel codes from inference libraries like ArmNN and XNNPack, Luthier demonstrates a significant computational advantage, achieving up to a 2.0x speed improvement in various devices and processors. Moreover, by employing machine learning techniques to reduce profiling samples, Luthier reduces tuning time by 95% compared to existing methods such as AutoTVM and Ansor. This makes Luthier a highly efficient tool in enhancing the performance and efficiency of deep learning applications on diverse hardware platforms.

A.2 Data Availability Statement

The source code for this research work can be accessed publicly on Gitlab at the following URL: <https://gitlab.com/ones-ai/Luthier>

A.3 Description

A.3.1 Software

- Luthier with XNNPack (<https://github.com/google/XNNPACK>) performs workload distribution and kernel search based on Google’s deep learning acceleration library.
- XNNPack supports Intel, Arm, RISC-V, and WebAssembly universally, selecting kernels based on the type and architecture of the CPU. When performing operations, it utilizes pthreadpool (<https://github.com/Maratyszczka/pthreadpool>) to distribute the workload.
- Luthier Pthreadpool The conventional pthreadpool distributes the workload equally among all threads. If a thread finishes its tasks early, it exploits additional work from other threads to minimize inactive threads. Luthier Pthreadpool does not assign the same workload to every thread; instead, it varies the initial task allocation for each thread to minimize bottlenecks due to exploiting.
- Luthier with ArmNN
 - Luthier-Mali is a project for ACL’s Mali GPU, operating highly optimized kernels based on OpenCL.
 - Luthier-Neon, in conventional ACL, generates threads equal to the number of the lowest frequency cores and distributes the workload so that all threads perform identical tasks.

A.3.2 Log Data

The execution configuration is modified to run ARM Compute Library and XNNPack, generating logs that are used for

tuning purposes. Table 1 shows the execution logs generated for the ACL, while Table 2 displays the logs for XNNPack. Additionally, we provide execution logs generated on two embedded target boards, Edge R and Odroid N2+, to facilitate easy reproduction. The generated logs primarily contain latency information for all configurable settings based on exhaustive search.

Table 1. Description of Log Data in the Arm Compute Library

Field	Description
layer id	Unique layer identifier in ArmNN (internally determined)
layer name	Layer name specified in ArmNN
kernel name	Kernel name specified in ACL
conv id	Number to check for the presence of convolution (0: not a convolution, other numbers indicate convolution)
Alg.	Algorithm used for convolution operation in ACL (options include Winograd, W/O Direct, General (W/ Im2Col))
Conv simd	MicroKernel number used for performing convolution operations in ACL
Cluster0 workload	Amount of computation to be performed on the Littler Cluster
Cluster1 workload	Amount of computation to be performed on the Big Cluster
Core0	First CPU according to <code>cat /proc/cpuinfo</code> (corresponds to the Little Core in Odroid N2+)
Core1	Second CPU according to <code>cat /proc/cpuinfo</code> (corresponds to the Little Core in Odroid N2+)
Core2	Third CPU according to <code>cat /proc/cpuinfo</code> (corresponds to the big Core in Odroid N2+)
Core3	Fourth CPU according to <code>cat /proc/cpuinfo</code> (corresponds to the big Core in Odroid N2+)
Core4	Fifth CPU according to <code>cat /proc/cpuinfo</code> (corresponds to the big Core in Odroid N2+)
Core5	Sixth CPU according to <code>cat /proc/cpuinfo</code> (corresponds to the big Core in Odroid N2+)
Kernel Compute Time	Kernel operation time within ACL’s Scheduler (measurement range from thread start/stop call times)

A.3.3 Scripts

For easy-to-reproduce results, we provide the following shell scripts.

Table 2. Description of Log Data in the XNNPack

Field	Description
Index	Order of kernel creation
Kernel	Kernel name generated by TFLite
Layer	Layer name generated by TFLite
DataLayout	Data structure
Type	Data type
Gemm ID	Default is -1, the order of GEMM when all conditional branches are removed in XNNPack
Max Work Size	Total Workload in XNNPack
CPU0-5	Workload Distribution per Core
Score0-6	Kernel Compute Time in XNNPack (Measurement range: thread start/stop)

- `reproducibility.sh`: A script to reproduce Figure 7 from the paper.
- `show_layer_acl.sh`: A script to display data from previously executed logs.
- `show_layer_xnnpack.sh`: A script to display data from previously executed logs.
- `run.sh`: A script for creating a Docker environment to facilitate easy execution.
- `tune_acl.sh`: A script for tuning the ACL library.
- `tune_xnnpack.sh`: A script for tuning the XNNPack library.

Reproducibility of Experiments

A.4 Experiment Workflow

The complete experimental workflow—encompassing the construction of the Docker image, generation of tuning logs, adjustments based on these logs, and replication of figures from our study—typically requires a few hours to complete using this artifact. However, the log generation phase, which involves direct timing measurements on the actual hardware, can vary in duration depending on the execution configuration and the thermal conditions of the target board. When tuning is conducted using the provided logs, the process generally completes within an hour.

A.4.1 Tuning from existing logs

To facilitate precise replication of the figures presented in our paper, we supply logs that document execution times for predefined configurations. To initiate the tuning process using these logs (listed in Table 1 and Table 2), one should sequentially execute `run.sh` and `reproducibility.sh`. By adhering to the specified random seed values, Figure 7 from the paper can be accurately reproduced. The existing logs for reproducibility can be accessed publicly on Gitlab at the following URL: <https://gitlab.com/ones-ai/Luthier/>

```

uploads/0a7b3f3650f991f43f107b98f51a3723/log.
tar.gz

(host)$ python3 ./main.py
# Log format (Whether XNNPack or ACL)
--backend acl
# Search algorithms
--optimizer random,bayesian,xgboost,greedy
# Location of logs for ACL, XNNPack for search area
--directory ./log/acl_resnet18_on_odroid
# Number of times to repeat tuning
--tune_iteration 200
# Number of repetitions of tuning iterations
# (to calculate the max and min values for graphs)
--search_iteration 5
# ID of the layer that can be optimized
# from the log (--show_list to obtain)
--layer_id 259
# Title of the output Figure
--title_figure "ResNet18's Conv2"
# Location to save and filename
--save_output ./xnnpack_resnet18_conv2
# Save the current tuning results as a PDF
--save_figure
# Save as a pickle as well?
--save_save_pickle
# Seed values for experimental reproducibility
--random_seed_xgboost 1,2,3,4,5
# Seed values for experimental reproducibility
--random_seed_bayesian 6,7,8,9,10
# Seed values for experimental reproducibility
--random_seed_greedy 11,12,13,14,15
# Seed values for experimental reproducibility
--random_seed_random 16,17,18,19,20

```

An example of console output generated during the tuning process in Luthier is as follows:

```

INFO : [bayesian] iteration : 41, index: 36,
inference time : 2.528494625 ms, info:
{little: 36, big: 76, layer_id: 252, layer_name:
NeonConvolution2dWorkload_Execute,
kernel_name: 'CpuIm2ColKernel', 'conv_alg':
'im2col'}

INFO: Name of the Optimizer
(bayesian, xgboost, random)
iteration: Number of search iterations
Index: Index number of the csv file
used in the search
Inference time: Inference performance recorded
in the log

info:{
  little:
  Workload assigned to the Little cluster
  big:

```

```

    Workload assigned to the Big cluster
    layer_name:
    Layer name specified in ArmNN / XNNPack
    kernel_name:
    Kernel name specified in ACL / XNNPack
    conv_alg:
    Name of the convolution algorithm
    specified in ACL or XNNPack
}

```

The method for merging the experimental results performed on each board into a single plot is as follows.

```

python3 ./integrate.py
# Filename of the pickle saved with
# --save_output in ./main
# (pickle file for EdgeR or Odroid N2+)
--pickles
    "/edger_acl_resnet18_conv2.pickle"
    "/odroid_acl_resnet18_conv2.pickle"
# Name of title
--title "ResNet's Conv2"
# Output the final result
# (the same image as shown in the paper.)
--output "./result.pdf"

```

A.4.2 Generating Tuning Logs via Direct Execution

This section explains how to measure execution times on the Odroid N2+ and Edge R by running ACL and XNNPack directly, without using pre-provided logs, as the execution configuration changes. First, the following procedures are conducted in a Docker environment using a Dockerfile (execute run.sh).

```

# Prerequisite :
Docker, python 3.9, Ubuntu 20.04

(host) $ git clone --recursive
https://gitlab.com/ones-ai/acl-tuner-v2

(host) $ git clone --recursive -b develop
https://gitlab.com/ones-ai/Luthier

# Build the code on the host
(host) $ cd acl-tuner-v2 && make xnnpack && \
make armcpu && make mali

# Copy the compiled code to the target board
(host) $ scp -r [./XNNPack, ./Neon, ./Mali]
[board account]@[board IP]:/[path on the board
to copy to]

# Run on the target board
# (the target board requires an OS with
# Ubuntu 20.04 or higher installed)
# Measure latency while changing

```

```

# kernel selection and workload allocation
# through exhaustive search
(target) $ ./Luthier-opt.sh [model.tflite]

# Move logs from the target board to the host
(target) $ scp -r
./log [Host account]@[Host IP]:/[path to copy]

# Move logs from the Host PC to the log folder
# in Luthier.
(host) $ mkdir -p ./Luthier/log
(host) $ mv -r ./log ./Luthier/log

# Set up the environment for Cost Model
# training and
# searching for optimal Config values
# Need: 'Docker'
(host) $ cd ./Luthier/log && ./run.sh

# Train the Cost Model, search for
# the optimal Config values, and create graphs
# For Demo, ACL Layer 2(conv2) in Resnet18
(in container on host) $ ./script/tune_acl.sh

# Manual Option: Print layers that
# can be optimized from the log
(in container on host) $ python3 ./main.py \
--backend acl \
--directory ./log/acl_resnet18_on_odroid \
--show_list

```

Expected Output: [252 253 254 ...]

A.4.3 Artifact Dependence and requirements

To run Luthier, the following dependency packages and libraries are required. For easy environment setup, we provide a Dockerfile¹.

```

Requirements (Python 3.9)
    bayesian-optimization==1.4.3
    pandas==2.2.0
    numpy==1.26.2
    xgboost==2.0.3
    matplotlib==3.8.2
    matplotlib-inline==0.1.6
    scikit-image==0.22.0
    scikit-learn==1.4.2
    scipy==1.11.4

```

```

common:
    curl, wget
    tar, unzip
    make

```

¹<https://gitlab.com/ones-ai/acl-tuner-v2/-/blob/main/Luthier-XNNPack/Dockerfile>

arm gcc 8.3-2019.03
armnn: (base 22.05.1)
ubuntu: 18.0.4
cmake 3.31.8
protobuf 3.12.0
C++ 14
fmt MIT 7.0.1 <https://github.com/fmtlib/fmt>
ghc MIT 1.3.2 <https://github.com/gulrak/filesystem>
half MIT 1.12.0 <http://half.sourceforge.net>
mapbox/variant BSD 1.1.3 <https://github.com/mapbox/variant>
stb 2.16 <https://github.com/nothings/stb>
cxxopts: 12e496da3d486b87fa9df43edea65232ed852510
(<https://github.com/jarro2783/cxxopts>)
Luthier:
HappyHTTP (<https://github.com/Piorosen/HappyHTTP>)
nlohmann/json
(<https://github.com/nlohmann/json/tree/v3.11.1>, 3.11.2)
tensorflow-lite 2.5.0: (library)
flatbuffer 1.2.0 (library)
bazel 3.1.0 (program)
python 3.9
acl: (base 22.05)
C++ 14
ubuntu: 18.0.4
scons
python 3.9
half MIT 1.12.0 <http://half.sourceforge.net>
OpenCL 3.0
xnnpack:
ubuntu: 18.0.4
cmake 3.31.8
arm gcc 8.3-2019.03
pthread: (based on git commit : 4fe0e1e1)
tensorflow-lite: 2.8.0
bazel 6.1.0
python 3.9